

STUDIES IN THIAZOLES. PART IV. PREPARATION OF SOME 2-BROMOTHIAZOLES

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2-Bromo-4-substituted thiazoles have been synthesised by the treatment of ω -thiocyanoacetophenones with hydrobromic acid gas in dry ether.

The method available in literature for the preparation of 2-bromothiazoles consists in diazotising 2-aminothiazoles in presence of 30% aqueous hydrobromic acid (Wibaut and Jensen, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1934, 53, 77) and the yields by this method are not satisfactory. In a previous attempt (Bariana, Sachdev and Narang, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 428) to prepare 2-bromothiazoles by saturating with hydrobromic acid gas an ethereal solution of ω -thiocyanoacetophenone, 2-hydroxy-4-phenylthiazole was found to be the only product in place of the required 2-bromo-4-phenylthiazole.

The sustained efforts in the field reveal that it is absolutely necessary to employ a solvent, which should be free from moisture, and the temperature of the reaction should be below 0°.

The possible mechanism leading to the formation of 2-bromothiazoles is as follows :

The traces of moisture possibly facilitate the addition of OH^- in place of Br^- in the intermediate (II), and thus give rise to 2-hydroxythiazoles by proceeding through the following sequence :

2-Bromothiazoles are fairly stable towards aqueous treatments of acidic or neutral solutions and have little tendency to hydrolyse with cold aqueous alkalis. Further work on the synthesis of 2-bromothiazole with various substitutions in the thiazole moiety is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Bromo-4-phenylthiazole.— α -Thiocyano-acetophenone (10 g.), dissolved in dry ether (250 c.c.), was cooled in a freezing mixture. It was saturated with dry hydrobromic acid for about 2 hours and allowed to stand for further 3 hours. The solvent was removed by distillation and the solid so obtained was treated with sodium carbonate solution, and filtered. On crystallisation from dilute ethanol it furnished a white solid, m.p. 55°, yield 8.0 g. (Found: S, 13.60. $C_9H_7NB_2S$ requires S, 13.33%).

TABLE I
2-Bromo-4-substituted thiazoles.

Compound.	Formula.	M.P.	Yield.	Found.	Calc.
2-Bromo-4-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl)-T	$C_9H_6NBrClS$	110°	70.8%	N: 5.23	5.24
2-Bromo-4-(<i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl)-T	$C_{12}H_{10}ONBrS$	105°	60.8	N: 4.72	4.93
2-Bromo-4-(<i>p</i> -bromophenyl)-T	$C_9H_5NB_2S$	120°	86.6	Br: 50.70	50.15
2-Bromo-4-(<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl)-T	$C_{10}H_9ONBrS$	135	50.6	N: 5.57	5.18
2-Bromo-4-(<i>p</i> -ethylphenyl)-T	$C_{11}H_{10}NBrS$	60-61	61.0	N: 5.06	5.22
2-Bromo-4-(<i>p</i> -methylphenyl)-T	$C_{10}H_9NBrS$	89-90	80.0	C: 47.96 H: 3.35	47.24 3.15
2-Bromo-4-(4'-methyl-6'-hydroxy-phenyl)-T	$C_{10}H_9ONBrS$	165	60.1	N, 5.35	N, 5.18

Note: Ethanol was used as the solvent for the crystallisation of the compounds.

T denotes thiazole.

A similar experimental procedure was adopted for the preparation of some other 2-bromo-4-substituted thiazoles (Table I). In some cases α -thiocyano-ketone did not dissolve in the requisite amount of ether, which, however, dissolved as the reaction proceeded in the forward direction.